

**LIVED EXPERIENCES OF SOCIAL STUDIES TEACHERS IN TEACHING
GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION IN JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL:
A PHENOMENOLOGICAL APPROACH**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 7

Pages: 772-785

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2098

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12867265

Manuscript Accepted: 06-20-2024

Lived Experiences of Social Studies Teachers in Teaching Global Citizenship Education in Junior High School: A Phenomenological Approach

Lhea Gracielle B. Victa, Joseph A. Asuncion, Ligaya Z. Del Rosario, Liningning B. De Castro,
Vivian I. Buhain, Luzale D. Henson

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This qualitative phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of five junior high school teachers teaching GCE at Judge Juan Luna High School. Data were collected through in-depth, semi-structured interviews and analyzed using Moustakas' transcendental phenomenological approach. This study was anchored on Social Constructivism and Transformative Learning theory. The findings revealed that teachers viewed GCE as an educational process that fosters responsible global citizens exhibiting tolerance, respect, and belonging to the global community. GCE concepts were seen as part of the broader Social Studies curriculum taught through an interdisciplinary lens. Teachers observed positive transformations in students, such as increased empathy, critical thinking, and community engagement. However, challenges included limited student interest, navigating sensitive topics, lack of resources, and overcoming cultural barriers. Teachers employed strategies like interactive methods, contextualizing lessons, and student-centered learning to engage students in GCE. The study highlighted the need for professional development, training, contextualized materials, and collaboration to enhance GCE instruction effectively. Teachers expressed hopes for GCE to nurture equality, peace, critical thinking, and active global citizenship among diverse individuals. The implications emphasize comprehensive training, curriculum integration, innovative assessments, community involvement, and promoting cultural sensitivity to prepare responsible global citizens.

Keywords: *global citizenship education, junior high school teachers, lived-experiences, social studies*

Introduction

Global Citizenship Education refers to an educational approach that emphasizes the development of critical thinking skills and a sense of shared humanity. It involves teaching students about global issues such as poverty alleviation, climate change mitigation, and human rights advocacy across cultures and borders (Witt 2022). It goes beyond traditional subject-specific instruction by focusing on developing critical thinking skills, empathy, cultural competence, and ethical awareness among students (Wijanarko, 2020). Cultivating these qualities within students' minds from an early age through education systems worldwide could contribute to shaping responsible global citizens.

Education plays a crucial role in promoting global citizenship by developing individuals' sense of responsibility for groups at local, national, and global levels. It also fosters an understanding of the interdependence of social, economic, and environmental change at national and international levels. (Zahra, 2022). According to (Andrews, K., & Aydin, H., 2020), in the United States, they were constantly recognized as the foundation upon which they advocated for the necessity of global citizenship education in the pre-K-12 curriculum, as well as how it should be introduced into the curriculum and applied in the classroom. The participants in the current study recognized changing societal demands for transforming from local citizenry to global citizenry as a response to increased diversity in United States schools and students needing tools and resources to become productive and proactive citizens in a global society.

Moreover, the Philippines' Department of Education (DepEd) plans to incorporate global citizenship topics into its MATATAG curriculum. MATATAG Curriculum means make the curriculum relevant to produce job-ready, active, and responsible citizens, take steps to accelerate the delivery of basic education services and provision of facilities, take good care of learners by promoting learner well-being, inclusive education, and a positive learning environment, and lastly, give support for teachers to teach better. The Bureau of Curriculum Development is updating the curriculum to align with international curricula, including integrating global citizenship education. The job market is evolving, necessitating the development of 21st-century skills like creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, and emotional and digital intelligence. As learners become more globally connected, they develop cultural awareness and global citizenship skills, but also face international crises, causing anxiety. The importance of lifelong learning and resilience is growing, and education systems must foster adaptive learning environments. An improved curriculum integrates contemporary topics, cultivates 21st-century skills like critical thinking and digital literacy, and promotes flexibility and adaptability. It also enhances inclusivity by teaching about global citizenship and diversity, promoting a future-oriented mindset. This empowers learners to become future leaders. (Republic of the Philippines Department of Education Bureau of Curriculum Development, 2023).

Teachers are identified as crucial actors in global citizenship education, playing a pivotal role in helping students become engaged and transformational global citizens. (Khalid et al., 2022). However, teacher's understanding and awareness of global citizenship education vary considerably (Karatekin, 2022). The challenges faced by teachers in implementing global citizenship education within the social studies curriculum are multi-faceted. Firstly, time constraints pose a significant challenge as teachers are often required to cover a vast amount of content within limited class hours. This allows little room for integrating additional topics related to global issues (Lukman,

2021). Secondly, inadequate access to suitable teaching resources is another obstacle that hinders effective implementation. Without proper materials and tools that address global perspectives, teachers struggle to create engaging lessons that foster students' understanding of the interconnectedness and promote critical thinking (Wijanarko, 2020). Finally, limited professional development opportunities focused on enhancing teachers.

Upon analyzing the relevant literature, studies have been conducted on the concept of global citizenship and global citizenship education at primary school, middle school, secondary school, and later periods. One research was conducted with eight Early Childhood Education students and ten Health Sciences students regarding Service-Learning as Global Citizenship Education: Acting Locally on Global Challenges and Concerns (Adarlo, 2020). However, few such study has examined junior high school teachers' perspectives on the concept of global citizenship and has been published. In Judge Juan Luna High School, they are the ones in charge of fostering a sense of global citizenship among the students. Therefore, it is crucial to ascertain their opinions on the subject. The findings of this study will guide additional research.

Research Questions

The purpose of this transcendental phenomenological approach was to explore the lived experiences of Social Studies teachers in teaching Global Citizenship Education in Junior High School at Judge Juan Luna High School, Quezon City. This stage in the research teaching Global Citizenship Education generally defined as an approach to education that helps individuals develop the skills, knowledge, and values they need to become active, responsible, and responsive citizens who contribute to building more peaceful, just, and sustainable societies. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of junior high school teachers teaching global citizenship education?
2. What are the participants' approaches to challenges and problems?
3. How were the insights drawn from the study enhanced the teaching-learning process in implementing Global Citizenship Education?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a qualitative transcendental phenomenological design to have a brief description of experience and reflection on teaching Global Citizenship Education in Social Studies in junior high school classes. Their feelings would be explored and explained through descriptive phenomenology. Qualitative research is a type of study that digs deeper into issues in the actual world by gathering participant experiences, perceptions, and actions (Tenny et. al., 2022). This study aimed to address the concerns and other flexible questions relating to teaching Global Citizenship Education in Social Studies in junior high school classes. On its essence, qualitative research asks open-ended questions like "how" and "why," whose answers are difficult to quantify.

Phenomenological research focused on discovering the significance that people attribute to their experiences and exploring the essence of human experiences. It does not impose ideas or explanations; instead, it aims to capture the core components and underlying structures of these experiences. To hear and document secondary educators' experiences with global education, the researcher selected a qualitative transcendental phenomenological methodology for this study (Moustakas, 1994). Grounding the methodology in Husserl's philosophical tradition that reality can be discovered only after transcending experience (Kafle, 2013), Moustakas (1994) sought "to see phenomena through unclouded glasses, thereby allowing the true meaning of phenomena to naturally emerge with and within their own identity" (Sheehan, 2014, p. 10). Thus, transcendental phenomenology is "focused less on the interpretations of the researcher and more on a description of the experiences of participants" (Creswell & Poth, 2018, p. 78). Additionally, transcendental phenomenology requires that researchers bracket out their own biases and experiences with the phenomenon being studied to gain a pure understanding of the phenomenon as described by the participant (Moustakas, 1994).

Participants

The sample participants of the study were five Social Studies teachers teaching GCE. They were selected using purposive sampling to meticulously select the participants. According to Frost, 2022, purposive sampling is a non-probability technique where researchers select particular participants who will help the study achieve its objectives by using their experience. The researchers must consider these participants' unique traits when assessing their research question.

The researcher purposely selected five (5) participants who actively teach Global Citizenship Education in Social Studies in junior high school classes at Judge Juan Luna High School based on the criteria to gather quality insights. In other words, units are selected "on purpose" in purposive sampling. This sampling strategy, also known as judgemental sampling, focuses on the researcher's judgment in identifying and selecting individuals, cases, or events that can provide the greatest amount of information to accomplish the study's objectives.

Instruments

The researcher used three different methods in gathering needed data in accordance to achieve the objectives of the study such as

interview, observation, and documents.

Interview is regarded as one of the most frequently used data collection tools in qualitative studies. It's a method of gathering data that gives the researcher(s) the chance to obtain information in a more detailed way through verbal communication concerning how and in which conditions, thoughts, and behaviors vary in such cases (Karasar, 2012; Seidman, 2006). This research employed a semi-structured interview method. Semi-structured interviews are the most widely used data collection tools in phenomenological research. Semi-structured interviews are conducted using preset questions in this manner; however, interviewers are permitted to ask additional questions for clarification as needed. (Taherdoost, 2022).

Observation. The researcher used qualitative observation to conduct the study, interact, and get additional data that supports the needed data on the lived experiences of social studies teachers in teaching Global Citizenship Education in junior high school. Gathering "open-ended, firsthand information" is necessary for researchers to study behavior (Creswell, 2012, p. 213). The researcher used informal observation to triangulate data obtained through interviews. Observed how the lived experiences of the teachers at school such as. their teaching strategies, their behavior inside the classroom and how they manage difficult situations inside the classroom

Documentation This qualitative phenomenological study use visual documentation to capture and comprehend participants' actual experiences. It allows people to add images linked to their personal experiences with the phenomena underresearch. This participative technique empowers participants by ensuring that the images are meaningful and relevant to them, as word representations alone may not capture the complexities and profundity of these experiences.

Procedure

Several steps were taken to guarantee accurate and ethical data collecting throughout the actual data collection period. Before the interview, each participant signed an informed consent form to protect confidentiality. Once approval was granted, two informed consent forms were prepared and signed, with one copy provided to the participant and the other retained for documentation. Eligible participants were selected based on inclusion criteria, one-on-one interviews were conducted by the researcher with interview guide questions provided to explore the experiences of social studies teachers with regards to GCE. Participants had opportunities to ask for clarifications if there were unclear questions to gain a deeper understanding of their experiences. Prior to the interviews, the researcher introduced herself and clarified the study's purpose, objectives, and significance to the participants.

The researchers collected data through purposive interviews, which were transcribed verbatim by the researcher, and a written text of each interview was created. The participants' identities were removed from the transcripts to maintain their confidentiality, and pseudonyms were assigned to participants to protect their identities while providing information relating to their backgrounds. Additionally, daily teaching activities of the participants was observed and recorded to validate and cross-examine their responses during the interview.

Ultimately, a debriefing session was held so that all of the participants could express their emotions about the interview. After thanking the participants for their time, the researcher asked one last clarifying question to wrap up the interview. The gathered data was then encoded, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted to arrive at meaningful conclusions. These procedures ensure that ethical and accurate data was collected, that can then be used to advance the understanding of social studies teachers in teaching GCE.

Data Analysis

All qualitative analysis included understanding the phenomenon being studied, presenting the phenomena while considering connections and associations, theorizing these connections and points of similarities, and eventually re-contextualizing the findings (Thorne, 2000). All collected data were encoded, recorded, analyzed, and interpreted utilizing themes and coding and fully analyzed depending on participant responses. Since this is qualitative the researcher performed content and narrative analysis based on the participant's responses to the open-ended questions.

For the content analysis, the researcher employed Moustakas' (1994) Transcendental Framework analysis, extracting codes from the responds, classifying them, and eventually finding themes through meticulous analysis, interpretation, and contextualization. The approach adopted aided in the transformation of qualitative data, allowing the researcher to draw valid conclusions regarding the lives of Social Studies teacher. The researcher then performed a manual content analysis on the collected data to discover patterns, themes, or codes, which were subsequently evaluated by themes and sub-themes.

Furthermore, the study employed narrative analysis as a method to analyze the participant's narratives and gain important understanding of the complexity of their testimonies, lives, emotions, and actions as Social Studies teachers teaching GCE in junior high school. Therefore, this method gives the researcher a thorough understanding of the real-world experiences in order to draw conclusions about the participants using the eight step laid out by Moustakas (1994). The eight steps are the following:

Horizontalization

In this process the researcher reads and rereads the verbatim transcription to list and categorize the participants' significant responses. Every relevant piece of information, including words, phrases, sentences, and emotional reactions, will be captured while all data will be treated equally. The goal is to uncover specific themes, experiences, or important points within each social studies teachers story.

Reduction and Elimination

By minimizing and eliminating unnecessary data, this procedure identified the invariant constituents. The information will be analyzed by the researcher to see if it can be reduced to its latent meaning and if it is pertinent to the participant's lived experience. It also eliminates content that seems to repeat, overlap, or be unclear. The researcher will keep data pertinent to the phenomenon and eliminate data that is not relevant to this study.

Clustering and Thematizing

During this process, all data gathered will be clustered to form themes and sub-themes. It entails categorizing qualitative data sets and using those categories as cluster or theme variables. This method assists the researcher in identifying themes and patterns in data that are relevant to the research but not relevant to the phenomena of the study.

Validation

The researcher consulted with an adviser to ensure the interview guide question aligned with the study's objectives. After a consultation, the researcher made necessary arrangements as per the adviser's instructions, ensuring the tool was in line with the research objectives.

Individual Textual Description

The researcher created personalized textual descriptions by using relevant, confirmed invariant components and themes, as well as verbatim extracts from transcriptions.

Individual Structural Description

Each participant in this process has developed a structural description, grounded on the data, of their lived experiences. To obtain a more accurate analysis and interpretation of the data in this case, thorough comprehension and investigation are necessary.

Textural-Structural Description

This process is also known as Synthesis. In this process, the researcher began to combine textual and structural data to provide in-depth analysis and interpretation of the phenomena to create themes and sub-themes that best described the lived experience of teachers in teaching Global Citizenship Education in Social Studies in junior high school classes.

Essence

From the structural and textual descriptions, the researcher then writes a composite description that presents the essence of the phenomenon. Primarily this passages focuses on the common experiences of the participants of the study.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical review considerations to be addressed below include issues related to confidentiality and consent, the right to withdraw, risks of participation, and data storage (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). All participants will be assigned a pseudonym and will be notified of their right to withdraw from participation in the study at any stage of the research study (Creswell, 2009). The participants' identities were remained confidential and safeguards participants' privacy and sensitive data through secure storage. The participations carry no known risks. By providing the interview questions to participants in advance and assuring them during the interview and in the consent letter that they have the right to decline to answer any question they find uncomfortable, as well as restating their right to withdraw from participation. Before the start of the data analysis, participants have a chance to go over the transcripts and make any corrections or withdraw any claims. All data in the form of audio recordings will be stored on a password-protected laptop/phone and will be destroyed after five years. The participants were asked to sign a consent letter (see Appendix A) giving their consent to be interviewed as well as audio-recorded. This consent letter provides an overview of the study addresses ethical implications and specifies expectations of participation.

Results and Discussion

Participants' Demographic Profile

The five participants of this qualitative research are Junior High School teachers at Judge Juan Luna High School, Quezon City and they were selected through purposeful criterion sampling. All participants were regular-permanent public junior high school teachers who taught Social Studies subjects. They taught Global Citizenship Education in their respective classes. Pseudonyms were used to assure anonymity among participants.

Table 1. Summary of Participants Demographic Profile

<i>Pseudonyms</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Years of Teaching Experience</i>	<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Teaching Position</i>	<i>Educational Attainment</i>
Rey	M	49	17	Grade 7	Master Teacher II	Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Social Studies

Sonia	F	28	6	Grade 7 and Grade 9	Teacher II	Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in History
Caryll	F	32	9 and 2 months	Grade 10	Teacher III	Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in History
Maryvhic	F	33	11	Grade 8 and Grade 10	Teacher III	Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Social Science
Bernie	M	60	10	Grade 9	Teacher II	Bachelor of Arts Major in Political Science

Participant 1, Rey

Rey is a 49-year-old Grade 7 Social Studies teacher at Judge Juan Luna High School, is a Master Teacher II with 17 years of experience in Araling Panlipunan. He earned a Bachelor of Secondary Education with a specialization in Social Studies from City College of Manila and a Master of Arts in Education from Eulogio Rodriguez Institute of Science and Technology. Rey completed his doctorate in educational management at the University of Caloocan City. His experience has strengthened his career, allowing him to identify solutions for students facing various obstacles.

Participant 2, Sonia

Sonia is a 28-year-old serves as a Grade 7 & 9 Araling Panlipunan teacher at Judge Juan Luna High School. She is Teacher II with 6 years of teaching experience. She obtained her bachelor's degree in Secondary Education, Majoring in History, from the Philippine Normal University. Currently, she is pursuing her Master of Arts in Education, specializing in Philosophy of Education, at the University of the Philippines Diliman. Dedicated to advocating for teachers' rights and education-related causes, Sonia holds the position of Union Council District Representative for Junior High School at the Quezon City Public School Teachers Association. She is also an active member of the Alliance of Concerned Teachers.

Participant 3, Caryll

Caryll is a 32-year-old Grade 10 Social Science teacher at Judge Juan Luna High School. She is Teacher III with nine years and two months of teaching experience. She handled Araling Panlipunan 7-10 during her seven years of teaching in the public school. She obtained her bachelor's degree in Secondary Education, Majoring in History, from well-known university in Metro Manila. She also have a unit in Master of Arts in Education Major in Social Sciences.

Participant 4, Maryvhic

Maryvhic is a 33-year-old Grade 8 and Grade 10 Social Science teacher at Judge Juan Luna High School. She is Teacher III with 11 years of teaching experience. She taught Araling Panlipunan 7-10 during her 10 years of teaching in public school. She received her bachelor's degree in secondary education, majoring in social science, from the Philippine Normal University. She completed her academic requirement in her master's degree in social science at Polytechnic University of the Philippines.

Participant 5, Bernie

Bernie is a 60-year-old Grade 9 Social Science teacher at Judge Juan Luna High School. He is a Teacher II with 10 years of teaching experience. He handled Araling

Panlipunan 7-10 during his ten years of teaching in the public school. He graduated from a reputable Metro Manila institution with a Bachelor of Arts degree major in Political Science. He completed his academic requirement in master's degree in special education at University of Santo Tomas.

Theme 1: Understanding and Integration of GCE into the teaching and learning process

Global Citizenship Education (GCE) is viewed by social studies teachers as promoting global interconnectedness, with decisions affecting communities throughout the world. Teaching global citizenship enables students to build responsibilities and competencies for an interconnected world. While some consciously integrated GCE, others adhered to the curriculum.

Three categories arise from this theme, including one global community, integration into curriculum, and moral obligations. In Category 1: One Global

Community, the understanding of GCE among educators is rooted in the idea that people are all interconnected in a global community. The rapid advancements in technology have revitalized the concept of GCE, emphasizing the impact of our decisions on a local, national, and international scale. Participants view teaching global citizenship as an essential aspect of education in a globally interconnected world. The participants emphasized that GCE helps students develop a sense of responsibility towards the global community and equips them with the knowledge and competencies needed to navigate an interconnected world.

For instance, Participant 1 Rey, *“These rapid developments have given new life to Global Citizenship, which holds that we are all part of one global community and that our decisions and actions may affect people and communities locally, nationally, and internationally.*

“L7-L9, Participant 3 Caryll, Global Citizenship Education, is an educational process that helps an individual to understand, to participate and to be a responsible citizen of the civil society” L5-L6

Moreover, the participants emphasized that GCE helps students develop a sense of responsibility towards the global community and equips them with the knowledge and competencies needed to navigate an interconnected world.

As Participant 2 Sonia mentioned, *“GCE helps young people gain the skills to engage with the world critically and thoughtfully.” L6-L7.*

According to (Rapoport, A. 2020) Global Citizenship Education concludes to enable citizens to change their way of life and adopt modern education for their benefit. It also fosters a shift in thinking toward diverse cultures, supporting global peace and harmony. This leads to connect to the large context. Aside from understanding what GCE is, participants also integrate it to the curriculum. In Category 2: Integration into Curriculum participants mentioned that GCE is part of the broader curriculum but they connect it to their lessons

As mentioned by Participant 1 Rey, *“It is always found in the lesson's application part.” L14-L15* also Participant 2 Sonia emphasized that, *“Although GCE is part of the broader curriculum framework, primarily addressed in Grades 4 and 10” I integrate it into my Grade 9 lessons intentionally. By incorporating GCE into the lessons, especially during the valuing component, I can help students develop a more comprehensive understanding of global issues and their role in the world. This approach allows me to guide students in critical thinking and active engagement with real-world challenges, even outside the designated grade levels.” L15- L21*

Additionally, teaching GCE is like teaching Social Studies subjects and it is best taught through integration or in interdisciplinary approach to enhance the teaching and learning process.

Participant 1 Rey stated, *“Teaching global citizenship is like teaching social studies subjects in all of its sub-disciplines: Asian and World History, Economics, and Current Issues in secondary schools. Because it is part of social studies instruction, how students internalize their reasons through reflection.” L12- L14* also Participant 4 Maryvhic, *“Araling Panlipunan is best taught through an interdisciplinary approach, integrating concepts from various disciplines such as social studies, geography, history, and economics. This approach helps my students understand global issues from multiple perspectives” L12-L15.*

According to one study, policymakers must highlight the significance of GCE by providing policy guidelines that promote its inclusion, in the curriculum. In order to promote a global perspective in all fields of study, it is crucial to implement courses and integrate global citizenship education (GCE) principles throughout the curriculum, pedagogy, and field placements, as well as prioritize professional development for teacher educators (Lourenço et al., 2022; Witt, 2022). Moreover, (Andrews & Aydin, 2020), including global citizenship education in the social studies curriculum would give teachers a way to introduce students to diversity and different cultures. Despite of integrating it to their lessons or subjects social studies teachers comply fully to their duty as educator. In Category 3: Moral Obligation they perceive education as a means to promote human rights and peace, underscoring their commitment to providing quality education that equips learners with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes to thrive in a diverse and interconnected world.

Participant 4 Maryvhic stated that, *“Teachers in Public Schools adhere to the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS) designed by the Department of Education. MELCS refers to the knowledge, understanding, skills, and attitudes that our students need to demonstrate in every lesson and/or learning activity in our subject area.” L17- L20* also Participant 3 Caryll, *“It is also my duty as an educator to provide my learners a quality education with knowledge, skills and attitudes that cultivate tolerance, respect, and a shared sense of belonging to one global community” L14- L16.*

As a result, this would enable students to gain an appreciation and understanding of cultures other than their own as well as the skills necessary to ensure that their perspectives and actions support becoming global citizens, especially when combined with opportunities for applied critical thinking that teachers provide. Furthermore, secondary teachers that include global connections into their curricula recognize that they are global citizens and hope that their students will follow. (Wasilewski, S. M. 2019).

Theme 2 Student Transformation and Actions through GCE

Junior high school teachers witnessed significant changes in their students as a result of Global Citizenship Education (GCE), including increased empathy, proactive community engagement, and advocacy for change. Examples include student-led community service during the COVID-19 pandemic and environmental projects that promote sustainability. GCE promotes critical thinking and involvement with global concerns, resulting students responsible citizens who understand their roles in a global society.

Two categories were arise from this theme, proactive members of the society and civic responsibility. In Category 1: Proactive members of the society the majority of the junior high school teachers shared examples of significant transformations observed in students as a result of engaging with GCE concepts. They noted instances where students became more caring, empathetic, and proactive in their communities, taking action and advocating for change.

As stated by Participant 2 Sonia, *“I would like to say that I observed my students becoming more caring and empathetic members of their school, at the very least.” L30-L31* also Participant 3 Caryll, *“My learners become actively participate in their community and work with others to make the society more equal, fair and sustainable.” L19-L20* also Participant 4 Maryvhic, *“Through a variety of*

locally based community involvement activities. taking part in elections for the student government, organizing clean-up campaigns, and joining clubs and other school groups.” L27-L29.

Moreover, participants highlighted also the different activities that their students involved with that incorporated with the GCE concepts.

As emphasized by Participant 1 Rey, *“During the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic, the youth also took part in community service, where the concerns are for public health and safety.” L32-L33 also Participant 2 Sonia “The “Kabataan Kontra Kalat” (3K) project, led by my students, is a powerful example of the transformations I’ve seen from engaging with Global Citizenship Education (GCE) concepts. The project aimed to reduce daily waste by monitoring trash and encouraging students to bring their own tumblers and food containers. Through this initiative, students showed a strong sense of responsibility and teamwork, taking charge of environmental stewardship at school. ” L34-L38.*

There was a study that stated that GCE can change people's behaviors and encourage a more favorable attitude toward different cultures, supporting global peace and harmony. (Amna Saleem et al., 2022). Students that actively participate in the community develop their ability to engage with a variety of societal challenges.

In Category 2: Civic Responsibility They emphasized that perceiving youth as members of a global society and being aware of the challenges and opportunities that come with it helps develop their roles and responsibilities as citizens. Moreover, GCE boosts engagement with real-world problems by promoting active involvement in finding solutions, enabling students to gain practical experience and understand their potential impact on communities and the world. The teachers highlighted the positive impact of Global Citizenship Education (GCE) on their students' empathy, critical thinking, and engagement with global issues.

As mentioned by Participant 1 Rey, *“Seeing youth as members of a global society, as well as being aware of and accepting responsibility for the difficulties and possibilities that arise, helps them develop their roles and responsibilities as citizens.” L36-L38 moreover, Participant 2 Sonia stated that “Global Citizenship Education (GCE) enhanced my students' empathy by exposing them to diverse perspectives, sharpens critical thinking through analyzing complex issues, and boosts engagement with real-world problems by encouraging active involvement in solutions.” L44- L46, and lastly Participant 3 Caryll, “It will help my learners to become responsible citizen, good decision makers and problem solvers for a better and transformative world.” L27-L28.*

It emphasizes the importance of educators incorporating global connections and viewpoints into their classrooms to enhance students' 21st-century skills and make them change agents (Wasilewski, S. M. 2019). To make the world a better place, students must grasp their duties as global citizens and recognize the need of international solidarity while fighting for a cause. Understanding global issues and other cultures encourages students to advocate for social justice, equity, unity, human rights, and environmental sustainability. (Andrews & Aydin, 2020).

As a result, the teachers consider GCE as a catalyst for developing responsible citizens who are empathetic, critical thinkers, and actively engaged in resolving global challenges. They view GCE as a transformative educational approach that equips learners with the necessary skills and mindset to become effective decision-makers and problem-solvers, contributing to a better world.

Theme 3: Emerging Problems in GCE

Global Citizenship Education (GCE) is not without its obstacles, as junior high school teachers interviewed about. Student interest and engagement, a lack of resources, negotiating different points of view, and handling sensitive topics are typical problems. There were worries that pandemic-related learning gaps may affect students' comprehension of difficult global issues. The delivery of lessons was hampered by a lack of instructional resources.

Two categories arise from this theme, Educational Difficulties and a broad range of focus. In Category 1: Educational Difficulties participants encountered different challenges when it comes to delivering the lessons one factor was the learning materials available in the school.

Participant 3 Caryll mentioned that, *“We don’t have textbooks in AP10 , Sensitive topic, Cultural Diversity/Cultural Gaps” L32 also Participant 2 Sonia, “Limited resources, such as shortages in teaching materials and visual aids make delivering engaging lessons more difficult.” L51-L54.*

Aside from this, participants also emphasized student engagement and external factors were also a challenge in teaching GCE.

Participant 4 Maryhic pointed out, *“Most learners in the public school have short attention spans. Keeping them engaged and interested in GCE can be a hurdle, as the concepts can be complex and abstract for some students.” L42-L44, also Participant 1 Rey “Given the many external factors influencing them, such as financial help, family background, and other relevant concerns.” L43-L44 and Participant 2 Sonia stated that, learning gap from the pandemic, which affects students' ability to grasp complex global issues” L50- L51.*

In classrooms, there is often a problem with student engagement. This problem is mostly caused by the fundamental problem of students' lack of interest (Scholarworks@gvsu & Urias, 2022). The study found that while the majority of teachers believed it was their

duty to motivate and engage their learners, fewer of them thought that their students were inspired and engaged (Dissertations & Projects, 2019). These are some of the problems that need to be addressed in order to effectively teach to the students.

Moreover, in Category 2: Broad range of focus is another challenge that the participants faced was a wide range of topics needed to teach or cover to the students. The focus of GCE encompassed different areas such as political, economic, and cultural framework issues. As a result, teachers need to have differing viewpoints to effectively teach the lessons to their students to avoid misunderstandings when teaching the lesson to foster different skills such as empathy and critical thinking to their students.

Participant 1 Rey mentioned, *“It is focusing more on the political, economic, and cultural framework issues.”* L46, also Participant 4 Maryvhic mentioned, *“Teaching Global Citizenship Education (GCE) presents unique challenges due to its focus on global issues and sensitive topics requiring diverse teaching materials and navigating differing viewpoints, yet fostering essential skills like empathy and critical thinking.”* L49-L51.

As a result, teachers need to have differing viewpoints to effectively teach the lessons to their students to avoid misunderstandings when teaching the lesson to foster different skills such as empathy and critical thinking to their students.

Theme 4: Strategies to Address GCE Challenges

Participants highlighted cross-curricular integration of Global Citizenship Education (GCE) for junior high schools, creative teaching strategies, and parental involvement. It was emphasized to be culturally sensitive, to accommodate diversity, and to provide richer learning opportunities. To overcome obstacles, educators used a variety of pedagogical strategies, created inclusive learning environments, and increased student involvement using techniques like group projects and multimedia materials.

Two categories arise from this theme, Involve stakeholders and utilize various strategies. In Category 1: Involve stakeholders, this has proven as an essential strategy to combat the challenges that they are facing in teaching GCE in junior high school classes.

Participant 4 Maryvhic pointed out that *“teachers should involve the local community in GCE initiatives, such as inviting guest speakers, organizing community service projects, or participating in global awareness events. Involving the local community in meaningful ways will help our students in understanding the connections between local and global issues and the importance of taking action at both levels.”*L71-L75, Participant 1 Rey also added *“Not only continuous discovery and development of innovative teaching but also to intensify the participation of parents in this endeavor.”* L56-L57.

Collaboration among players, especially non-governmental organizations and civil society organizations, is regarded as necessary for effective global citizenship education teacher education (Tarozzi, M. 2020). Aside from this, participants used different strategy to fully resolve the challenges In Category 2: Utilize various teaching strategies junior high school teachers exhibited various teaching strategies to engage students in teaching GCE inside the classroom.

Participant 1 Rey mentioned *“Teaching GCE among learners can be handled in a pedagogical and inventive way. Lecture-discussion, performance task, and homework-based, besides the use of social networking applications and other forms of technology”* L48-L50. also Participant 4 Maryvhic, *“we need to use a variety of teaching methods, such as group work, case studies, simulations, and multimedia resources, to make GCE more interactive and engaging for our students.”* L65-L67 moreover, Participant 4 Maryvhic added that *“I should focus on student-centered learning approaches, encouraging my students to take ownership of their learning and explore global issues that are meaningful to them”* L69-L7.

Similarly, according to (Chandresh Kumar Chhatlani, 2023), Holistic learning approaches, such as project-based and experiential learning, play an important role in developing global citizenship abilities. These initiatives foster multicultural understanding, empathy, effective communication, social justice awareness, environmental stewardship, and a feeling of civic responsibility among students. Holistic learning involves students in active learning, critical thinking, and reflection by combining real-world experiences with multidisciplinary views, training them to be responsible global citizens.

In order to develop responsible global citizens, social studies teachers placed a high priority on educational approaches that promote meaningful involvement, active learning, and cultural sensitivity.

Theme 5: Pointers for Development

Participants highlighted innovative teaching approaches, parental involvement, and cross-curricular integration of Global Citizenship Education (GCE) through a well-defined action plan for junior high schools. Providing culturally sensitive learning opportunities and acknowledging diversity were deemed critical. Participants also emphasized the need of integrating global concepts with local history and culture while contextualizing GCE for students. Seminars to revitalize instructional approaches were suggested, as well as annual workshops and regular updates on world events important to GCE. Educators' aspirations for GCE included developing future leaders, instilling agency, and responsibility, and creating a more interconnected global community.

In Category 1: Teaching is continuous learning, to improve teacher training and development in Global Citizenship Education (GCE), junior high school teachers proposed holding seminars and workshops that centered on revitalizing pedagogical competencies to successfully handle challenges in education. Most participants suggested offering continuing education programs that are especially

suited to GCE's dynamic nature, which mostly focuses on current events.

For instance, Participant 1 Rey mentioned that *“Conduct seminars and trainings on revitalizing pedagogical competencies by addressing educational challenges”* L60, L61, also Participant 2, Sonia *“Mentoring from experienced teachers and ongoing workshops can keep educators updated and well-prepared.”* L77-L78, also Participant 5 Bernie stated that *“Since GCE involves mostly of current events, teachers should be given an annual seminar-workshop and a quarterly update (thru letters, etc.) of the common interest (internationally) or events, or to how to be teach in Junior High School.”* L43-L45.

To integrate GCE in the teaching and learning process and parent involvement was another evident suggestions in the responses of the participants.

Participant 2, Sonia, stated *“I recommend integrating GCE into the Teacher Induction Program for new teachers. This provides foundational knowledge and strategies for teaching GCE effectively, including lesson planning, handling sensitive topics, and fostering empathy.”* L74-L77 also Participant 4, Maryhich, *“to integrate it with other subjects while meeting educational standards of DepEd. The MELCS should be aligned with the core concepts of global citizenship and not solely on historical facts and memorization. They should give teachers more freedom to tackle complex concepts regarding global citizenship”* L87- L90 also Participant 1 Rey pointed out *“Not only continuous discovery and development of innovative teaching but also to intensify the participation of parents in this endeavor.”* L56-L57.

There was a study that indicated that GCE success can be attributed to comprehensive policy frameworks, teacher training programs, and the inclusion of GCE throughout the curriculum (Dominici, 2022). In envisioning the future of Global Citizenship Education (GCE), the junior high school teachers emphasized the importance of nurturing students as future leaders and contributors to society. By encouraging students to translate their learning into action, they can cultivate a stronger sense of agency and responsibility, fostering a more just and sustainable world.

In Category 2, Positive Outlook is evident as stated by Participant 1 Rey *“We are one in dreaming for the best of our learners because they are our future generations. To achieve this endeavor, an educator should not lose hope”* L63-L65, Participant 2, Sonia *“By encouraging students to put their learning into practice, they can develop a stronger sense of agency and responsibility, becoming proactive contributors to a more just and sustainable world.”* L83- L85.

According to Pacho, T. O. (2020), Global citizenship education may not offer magic. It is possible to make a difference by developing solutions to the world's numerous challenges. It can develop essential and responsible global citizens; persons who can be proactive in changing the world around them and make the world a better place to live, work, and find fulfillment.

Structural Description

As stated by Moustakas (1994), one way to describe the context or setting that affects how participants experience an event is through the use of structural descriptions. The experiences of junior high school teachers are varied and complicated, influenced by various factors such as time, space, causality, materiality, relationship to others and self, and bodily factors, all of which affect in teaching GCE.

Time

According to Moustakas (1994), time is a description of an individual's experiences with a certain phenomenon in connection to time. In this research, the structural description focused on how the teachers participants experienced that the world as always changing and the need to continue reacting to these changes. Teaching GCE in schools requires a long term commitment and understanding that building global citizenship is a continuous process. As one participant mentioned, *“Our environment is growing increasingly complicated because of the widespread availability of information and communication technology. These rapid developments have given new life to Global Citizenship, which holds that we are all part of one global community and that our decisions and actions may affect people and communities locally, nationally, and internationally.”* L5-L9. Teachers must view it as a long-term target not just for students but for everyone.

Space

This is the descriptions of a person's lived-experiences that involves the situations when they faced or experienced the phenomena. (Moustakas, 1994). These teachers witnessed different transformations and actions from the students as a result of engaging with GCE concepts. Participants said that *“My learners become actively participate in their community and work with others to make the society more equal, fair and sustainable.”* L19-L20, *“Through a variety of locally based community involvement activities. taking part in elections for the student government, organizing clean-up campaigns, and joining clubs and other school groups”* L27-L29, *I witnessed a lot of youth advocacy towards global citizenship education in the community. During the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic, the youth also took part in community service, where the concerns are for public health and safety.”* L31-L33. These lines emphasized the importance of diverse learning spaces, both within and beyond the classroom, for fostering global citizenship. Additionally, the integration of GCE extend to co-curricular activities, community partnerships, and global collaborations, allowing students to experience global citizenship in various spatial contexts.

Casuality

It is the description of how certain factors have influenced a person's live experiences on the phenomenon. (Moustakas, 1994). In terms of casuality, participants faced different challenges in educational practices which influenced the participants' lived experiences of teaching Global Citizenship Education. participant stated that *"Evaluating my students' understanding and progress in GCE is also challenging, as traditional assessment methods may not always capture the full range of skills and competencies GCE aims to develop."* L34-L35. This line highlights the causal relationship between assessment strategies and the development of global citizenship competencies, underscoring the need for innovative assessment approaches. As a result, participant used different method in assessment *"Developing creative assessment strategies to evaluate my students' understanding of GCE, such as project-based assessments, portfolios, and reflective journals"* L36-L37.

Materiality

When it comes to materiality, it is the descriptions oh how the lived experiences of a person are affected by materiality or th reality of the world (Moustakas, 1994). In the study, teachers participants school conditions greatly affect their lives, as they struggle the availability or lack of material resources, such as textbooks and teaching materials, which can either facilitate or hinder their efforts. Participants are experiencing educational difficulties as stated during the interview, *"We don't have textbooks in API0"* L32, *"Limited resources, such as shortages in teaching materials and visual aids,"and with a lot of material thing that they lacked, they still managed to be resourceful and utilized only the available materials that they have"* L51-L53. Despite these challenges, the teachers emphasized the importance of finding creative solutions and adapting teaching approaches to effectively address the specific challenges of teaching GCE. *"Teaching GCE among learners can be handled in a pedagogical and inventive way. Lecture-discussion, performance task, and homework-based, besides the use of social networking applications and other forms of technology"* L48-L50, *"we need to use a variety of teaching methods, such as group work, case studies, simulations, and multimedia resources, to make GCE more interactive and engaging for our students."* L65-L67. These shows that the material concerns and the need for adequate educational resources are essential to effective teaching of GCE.

Bodily Concerns

It is the descriptions of a person's lived experiences which involves his/her body reactions such as emotions, etc. on the phenomenon. (Moustakas, 1994). Junior high school teachers face challenges in teaching in GCE like *"One challenge is teaching GCE, is how to inspire and motivate learners' interest in participating in at least a local community issue, given the many external factors influencing them, such as financial help, family background, and other relevant concerns."* L42-L44, "most learners in the public school have short attention spans. Keeping them engaged and interested in GCE can be a hurdle, as the concepts can be complex and abstract for some students." L42-L44. Here, the participants describes the bodily concern of motivating and inspiring students' interest in GCE, but also acknowledging external causes and concerns that may impact their level of engagement. Despite these challenges, teachers still have a positive outlook for their students and the future as mentioned by the participants *"I always assure and support my learners to gain an understanding of how the world works and try to stay well-informed"* L25-L26, *"we are one in dreaming for the best of our learners because they are our future generations. To achieve this endeavor, an educator should not lose hope, although the teaching profession is difficult to perform besides the personal problems that an educator also experiences."* L63-L65.

Relationship to Self and Others

Lastly, it is the descriptions of a person's live experiences involving their personal reactions, introspections and interactions with others as well. (Moustakas, 1994). When it comes to the participants' relationship to others and self, it was obvious that participants demonstrated a positive connection with themselves and others. For instance, participant mentioned that *"It is not far away from teaching social studies, values, and beliefs that molded my character as an educator."* L19-L22. *"even I am a Araling Panlipunan Teacher for years, I still need to learn and upgrade my skills and competencies."* L61-L62. The participants acknowledged that their expertise and competencies are constantly evolving, even after years of experience, and that teaching GCE aligns with their deeply held principles and fundamental aspects of their character as a teacher. Moreover, the participant values the ability to help students apply their learning to real-world situations, which is a core aspect of GCE. *"Global Citizenship Education (GCE) aligns with my values as an Araling Panlipunan educator by helping students apply what they learn to real-world situations"* L23-L24.

Essence

From the structural and textural descriptions, the researcher then writes a composite description that presents the "essence" of the phenomenon, called the essential, invariant structure (or essence). Primarily this passage focuses on the common experiences of the participants. (Moustakas, 1994). *"To make it more meaningful, learners should be asked to take part in such multitasking performances while the teacher encourages them to ask higher-order thinking questions for clarity and practical application."* L15-L17. This line captures the essence of GCE, emphasizing the development of higher-order thinking skills, practical application, and meaningful engagement with global citizenship concepts. At its core, the essence of GCE lies in nurturing responsible, ethical, and engaged global citizens who possess the knowledge, skills, and dispositions to navigate and contribute to an increasingly interconnected world. The essence of GCE is rooted in a commitment to social justice, sustainable development, and the promotion of human rights. By embodying these principles, students can become agents of positive change, actively participating in addressing global challenges and creating a

more just and equitable society.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Social Studies teachers understood Global Citizenship Education (GCE) as an educational process that fosters tolerance, respect, and a sense of belonging to the global community. They emphasized the importance of integrating GCE concepts into teaching, especially in Social Studies, where it is connected to geography, history, and economics. Teachers observed positive student transformations, including increased empathy, critical thinking, and engagement with global issues, and instances where GCE prompted students to advocate for change in their communities. Through these, it can be said that GCE really helps the students to become a global citizen with the help of their teachers.

Teachers faced challenges in teaching GCE, including lack of student engagement, cultural barriers, limited resources, and navigating sensitive topics. The pandemic and diverse student backgrounds exacerbated these issues. To address these, teachers employed strategies like relating concepts to students' experiences, using interactive methods, and contextualizing lessons with local events. They emphasized student-centered learning, encouraging students to take ownership of their learning and explore global issues. These challenges can hinder the teaching and learning process in GCE, employing different approaches in teaching and learning is highly suggested to attain the objectives.

The teachers recognized the need for professional development, training, and support from educational institutions and curriculum experts to enhance their knowledge, skills, and teaching strategies related to GCE. They expressed a desire access to contextualized resources and materials to improve their GCE instruction. This should prioritized in the education sector to fully integrate and teach GCE in junior high schools.

This qualitative study provided a descriptive understanding of social studies teachers' lived experiences in teaching Global Citizenship Education (GCE), suggesting that:

For students, they should actively engage in extracurricular activities, clubs, and community service projects to expand their understanding of diverse cultures and global issues. This promotes global awareness and social responsibility. Moreover, developing critical thinking skills, questioning assumptions, and seeking reliable information will help navigate the complexities of the interconnected world. Cultivating empathy and respect fosters a sense of global citizenship.

For Araling Panlipunan Teachers, continuously seek professional development opportunities such as workshops, seminars, or online courses to enhance their knowledge and pedagogical skills in GCE. In addition, they should integrate GCE concepts into other subjects through interdisciplinary lesson planning and activities that center on student-centered teaching methods that encourage critical thinking, discussion, and real-world application.

For Head Teacher of Araling Panlipunan, they develop a vision and plan for the entire school that incorporates GCE into extracurricular and curriculum activities. It is crucial to provide funds and assistance for GCE-related professional development opportunities for staff members and teachers. They should support and foster cooperation between educators from many topic areas in order to advance an interdisciplinary approach for the GCE. Additionally, developing collaborations with regional and international organizations as well as local residents may give students access to real-world learning opportunities and experiences.

For Education Supervisors, examine and revise curriculum and educational policies to ensure that GCE concepts and competencies are integrated across subjects and grades. Furthermore, developing guidelines and resources, such as lesson plans, teaching materials, and assessment tools, can help instructors adopt GCE successfully. It is also critical to organize teacher training programs and seminars that focus on teaching techniques, cultural sensitivity, and dealing with difficult GCE-related themes. Ultimately, they should cooperate with stakeholders such as teachers, students, parents, and community members to ensure GCE implementation is relevant and successful.

For Future Researchers, conduct larger-scale studies with more participants from diverse educational settings to enhance generalizability. Explore innovative, technology-enabled approaches for delivering GCE instruction and fostering global collaboration. Furthermore, investigating the contextual factors, such as cultural, socioeconomic, and educational systems, that influence the implementation and outcomes of GCE programs can provide valuable insights.

References

- Adarlo, G.M. (2017). (Re)framing Citizenship Education in the Philippines: A Twenty-First Century Imperative. *The Good Society*, 25, 256 - 288.
- Adarlo, G. M. (2020). Service-Learning as Global Citizenship Education: Acting Locally on Global Challenges and Concerns. *IAFOR Journal of Education*, 8(3), 7-23.
- Akpan, V. I., Igwe, U. A., Mpamah, I. B. I., & Okoro, C. O. (2020). *Social Constructivism: Implications On Teaching And Learning*.

- British Journal of Education, 8(8), 49–56. <https://www.eajournals.org/wp-content/uploads/Social-Constructivism.pdf>
- Alismaiel, O. A., Cifuentes-Faura, J., & Al-Rahmi, W. M. (2022). Online learning, mobile learning, and social media technologies: An empirical study on constructivism theory during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Sustainability*, 14(18), 11134.
- Amna Saleem, Farah Deeba, & Muhammad Aqeel Raza. (2022). Global Citizenship Education: A New Approach to Global Citizenship Development. *PERENNIAL JOURNAL of HISTORY*, 3(2), 392–409. <https://doi.org/10.52700/pjh.v3i2.131>
- Andrews, K., & Aydin, H. (2020). Pre-service teachers' perceptions of global citizenship education in the social studies curriculum. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 11(4), 84–113.
- Angyagre, S. E., & Quainoo, A. K. (2019). What are the critical dimensions in Ghana's senior high school social studies curriculum? Under the lens of a critical global citizenship education framework. *International Journal of Development Education and Global Learning*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.18546/ijdegl.11.2.02>
- Barry, M. (2020, November 1). Global challenges, global citizenship: what is the local classroom reality? A qualitative case study of global citizenship education teaching and learning practices. *Doras.dcu.ie*. <https://doras.dcu.ie/24983/>
- Barton, T. (2020, October 19). How global citizen education is impacted through service learning - Serve Learn. *Service Learning - Serve Learn*. Retrieved May 1, 2024, from <https://servelearn.co/blog/how-global-citizen-education-is-impacted-throu-gh-service-learning>
- Baysal, S., & Tanrıseven, I. (2020). Global Citizenship: From the Lens of the Education Faculty Instructors. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 16(5), 106–120. <https://doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2020.277.7>
- Bernardo, A. B. I., Cordel, M. O., Ricardo, J. G. E., Galanza, M. a. M. C., & Almonte-Acosta, S. A. (2022). Global Citizenship Competencies of Filipino Students: Using machine learning to explore the structure of cognitive, affective, and behavioral competencies in the 2019 Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics. *Education Sciences*, 12(8), 547. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12080547>
- Bercasio, R. R. O., & Perez, A. S. (2020). Global Citizenship Education in Bicol University Proposed Framework and Action Plan. *Bicol University R & D Journal*, 23(2).
- Bruce, J., North, C., & FitzPatrick, J. (2019). Preservice teachers' views of global citizenship and implications for global citizenship education. *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 17(2), 161–176.
- Burhanuddin, N. A. N., Ahmad, N. A., Said, R. R., & Asimiran, S. (2021). Learning theories: Views from behaviourism theory and constructivism theory. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 10(1), 85–98.
- Chandresh Kumar Chhatlani. (2023). Review the Role of Holistic Learning in Cultivating Global Citizenship Skills. 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.59652/jetm.v1i2.14>
- Coelho, D. P., Caramelo, J., Amorim, J. P., & Menezes, I. (2022). Towards the Transformative Role of Global Citizenship Education Experiences in Higher Education: Crossing Students' and Teachers' Views. *Journal of Transformative Education*, 15413446221103190.
- Delve. Ho, L., & Limpacher, A.(2022c, March 17). What is Phenomenological Research Design? Essential Guide to Coding Qualitative Data. <https://delvetool.com/blog/phenomenology>
- Dissertations, E., & Projects. (2019). Part of the curriculum and instruction commons, and the educational methods commons. https://digitalcommons.gardner-webb.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1352&context=education_etd
- Elhami, A., & Khoshnevisan, B. (2022). Conducting an interview in qualitative research: The modus operandi. *MEXTESOL Journal*, 46(1), 1–7. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1333875.pdf>
- Fatimah, S., Rosidin, D. N., & Hidayat, A. (2022). Student-based Learning in The Perspective of Constructivism Theory and Maieutics Method. *International Journal Of Social Science And Human Research*, 5(5), 1632–1637.
- Ferguson, C., & Brett, P. (2023). Teacher and student interpretations of global citizenship education in international schools. *Education, Citizenship and Social Justice*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17461979231211489>
- Frost, J. (2022, October 24). Purposive Sampling: Definition & examples. *Statistics by Jim*. <https://statisticsbyjim.com/basics/purposive-sampling/>
- Guajardo, M., & Vohra, S. (2023). Linking global citizenship education and critical pedagogy: Women's leadership and power. *Citizenship Teaching & Learning*, 18(2).
- Inclusivity, global citizenship to be expanded in DepEd's K to 12 curriculum. (2022, February 16). *Manila Bulletin*.

<https://mb.com.ph/2022/02/16/inclusivity-global-citizenship-to-be-expanded-in-d-epeds-k-to-12-curriculum/>

Instruction of Citizenship Education in Grade Four Social Studies Curriculum in Kenya. (2022). *Journal of Education and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.7176/jep/13-24-07>

Jalbani, L. N., & Khan, N. (2022). Analyzing Social Studies National Curriculum and Textbooks for the Concept of Global Citizenship: A Content Analysis. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.22555/joed.v9i1.422>

Karatekin, E. (2022). An examination of 1998 social studies textbooks in terms of UNESCO's global citizenship education paradigm. *Uluslararası Sosyal Bilimler Eğitimi Dergisi*, 8(1), 156–186. <https://doi.org/10.47615/issej.1102520>

Khalid, T., Muhammad, Y., & Siddiqui, M. (2022). Cultivating Global Citizenship among Secondary School Students: Pre-Service Teachers' Beliefs. *Global Social Sciences Review*, VII(II), 326–337. [https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2022\(vii-ii\).33](https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2022(vii-ii).33)

Lee, S. S. (2020). Fostering “global citizens”? Trends in global awareness, agency, and competence in textbooks worldwide, 1950–2011. *Prospects*, 48(3-4), 215-236.

Lourenço, M. (2021, April). From caterpillars to butterflies: Exploring pre-service teachers' transformations while navigating global citizenship education. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 6, p. 651250). Frontiers Media SA.

McLeod, S. (2024). The Zone of Proximal Development and Scaffolding. *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/Zone-of-Proximal-Development.html>

McLeod, S. (2024, January 24). Vygotsky's sociocultural theory of cognitive development. *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/vygotsky.html>

Pacho, T. O. (2020). Global Citizenship Education in the Era of Globalization. *Handbook of Research on Diversity and Social Justice in Higher Education*, 274–291. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-5268-1.ch016>

Republic of the Philippines Department of Education BUREAU OF CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT.(n.d.). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/GENERAL-SHAPING-PAPER-2023.pdf>

Saddiqa, T., Anwar, M. N., & Khizar, A. (2020). Global Citizenship Education in Pakistan: Awareness, Attitude and Challenges. *Global Educational Studies Review*, V(III), 315–326. [https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2020\(v-iii\).31](https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2020(v-iii).31)

Scholarworks@gvsu, S., & Urias, L. (2022). Addressing the problem of student engagement in the classroom Addressing the problem of student engagement in the classroom. <https://scholarworks.gvsu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1225&context=gradprojects>

Soares Carvalho, A. P., & Bignami, F. (2021). Social development through (global) citizenship education: the Brazilian case. *Intercultural Education*, 32(4), 464-475.

Schugurensky, D., & Wolhuter, C. (2020). Teachers' Education and Global Citizenship Education: An Introduction. In *Global Citizenship Education in Teacher Education* (pp. 1-19). Routledge.

Taherdoost, H. (2022, May 4). How to conduct an effective Interview; A guide to interview design in research study authors. <https://hal.science/hal-03741838>

UNESCO (2015) Incheon Declaration and Framework for Action for the implementation of Sustainable Development Goal 4, Paris: UNESCO

UNESCO (2015). SDG4-Education 2030, Incheon Declaration (ID) and Framework for Action. For the Implementation of Sustainable Development Goal 4, Ensure Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education and Promote Lifelong Learning Opportunities for All, ED-2016/WS/28.

Wasilewski, S. (2019). Global Citizenship Education: Secondary Teachers' Perceptions Of Global Education. All Theses and Dissertations. <https://dune.une.edu/theses/208/>

What is Global Citizenship Education? (2022). <https://www.globalcitizenshipfoundation.org/about/global-citizenship-education>

Wijanarko, H. (2020). Phenomenology studies in junior high school students' enthusiasm in social studies learning in Universitas Malang Laboratorium, Indonesia. *Harmoni Sosial: Jurnal Pendidikan IPS*, 7(2), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.21831/hsjpi.v7i2.31686>

Witt, A. (2022). Postpandemic futures of Global Citizenship Education for preservice teachers: Challenges and possibilities. *PROSPECTS*, 51(1), 11-21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-022-09599-5>

Zahra, A. (2022). UNESCO's Vision to Promote The dimensions of Global Citizenship in Education “Analytical Study in Light of The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.” *Port Said Journal of Educational Research*, 1(1), 1–35. <https://doi.org/10.21608/psjer.2022.155894.1002>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Lhea Gracielle B. Victa

San Juan Integrated School – Philippines

Joseph A. Asuncion, EdS, DPA

New Era University – Philippines

Ligaya Z. Del Rosario, PhD

New Era University – Philippines

Liningning B. De Castro, PhD

New Era University – Philippines

Vivian I. Buhain, EdD

New Era University – Philippines

Luzale D. Henson, PhD

New Era University – Philippines